

PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS AND SOCIAL ATTITUDES OF YOUNG PEOPLE GROWING UP IN INCOMPLETE FAMILIES

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Abstract. *The article covers the role and social problems of the dysfunctional family in society. The problems encountered in the psychology of children under the age of majority in a dysfunctional family and their classification have also been analyzed.*

Keywords: *incomplete family, child rearing, social adaptation, strong family, spirituality.*

The family is a unique barometer of power and society: family well-being is a guarantee of the stability of power, a strong family is established in a powerful, independent state. Therefore, the development and formation of the family, the creation of socio-economic, cultural and spiritual services for its life are the main factors for the future development of the young generation.

The family is a social institution where the formation of a person takes place, it becomes the first house where a person grows up and receives the first life lessons, support and help, learns to love the world and people. It is a place that warms his heart and keeps the best and brightest memories for life, which strengthens his bright will in the most difficult moments of his life. In the family, the father's indifference to his children will eventually lead to ugly consequences. Indifference is a bad habit, and it paves the way for the breakdown of child rearing. Due to the fact that the father was lazy, did not fulfill his duty and did not teach useful knowledge and good deeds, he could not form the necessary positive feelings in his child. The child also grows up without the good upbringing of his father. And the next period requires a little demandingness and discipline. This period is the period of adolescence, and it is at this time that the child distinguishes between black and white. He learns the inevitability of reward for good and punishment for evil from this stage. During this period, if the child is guided in the right way, accompanied by well-educated friends, an important step will be taken for him to be polite and become a good person.

In a word, the influence of the family on the formation of a child is very large, because education is a controlled socialization process. Ideally, it should be like this. But there is another side of the coin in life. The nature and behavior of the child depends on the environment in the family. Of course, good children do not grow up on their own, but grow up in the family under the supervision of their parents. Some recommendations have been given by our elders for the child to grow up well in all aspects. It consists of recommendations such as "Islam, knowledge, religion, contentment, discipline, conscience and patriotism, justice, chastity, patience and correctness" holds.

A dysfunctional family that shows and inculcates antisocial habits, attitudes, needs in a child, does not provide control, emotional support and protection from external negative influences, has a devastating effect on the formation of the moral characteristics of a minor.

Depending on the type and level of the problem, the classification of defective families is carried out. So far, there is no single classification, so we will focus on the most complete and interesting ones. In conclusion, we can determine the negative factors of family education that are characteristic of every unhealthy family at this level:

- improper influence on the material well-being of the family: excess (or lack) of things, material superiority.

- the disproportion of the well-being, material needs and opportunities to satisfy them, the violation, immorality and illegality of the family economy in the realization of the spiritual needs of a growing person;

- lack of spirituality of parents; lack of desire for children's spiritual development;

- authoritarianism or liberalism, impunity and forgiveness;

- immorality, presence of immoral style and tone of family relations, illegal lifestyle;

- lack of normal psychological climate in the family;

- fanaticism in any form (passion for collecting money and things, religious, political, musical, sports);

- illiteracy from a psychological-pedagogical point of view (unsuitability of education, dishonesty, inconsistency in the use of methods of education, corporal punishment, causing severe moral suffering to teenagers);

- inability (and sometimes unwillingness) to understand and accept the child as he is.

The listed negative factors of family education lead to the appearance of a number of the most typical mistakes in education, which appear under the influence of certain socio-psychological conditions.

The first typical mistake is the inconsistency between the actions of parents (as well as older family members). This situation disturbs the mental balance of the child and makes him nervous. The volume of the flow of various information on parenting issues by parents is constantly expanding (in particular, it is strongly influenced by the characteristics of urban society). In order to correctly accept it, master it and put it into practice, parents must constantly improve both as individuals and as educators. Only under these conditions, it is possible to guide children's behavior in a consistent and coordinated manner, to reorganize even unfavorable home conditions for the benefit of their development, to ensure that family education meets the requirements of the times (the pace of life and dynamic trends of development).

Conflicts in the family, nervousness in the relationship between parents and children, the relatively low cultural and educational level of a certain part of parents prevent the acquisition of pedagogical knowledge. Due to the dynamic pace of life, emotional instability creates a multifaceted family environment.

It is characterized by two poles: negative (anger, temper, etc.), if the behavior of adolescents leads to problems, and positive (parental love for children, regardless of what they are gaze). The two poles are in a complex dynamic relationship, which in turn helps to create an unbalanced, multi-directional pedagogical experience for parents.

The second common mistake is the largely unconscious lack of purposeful educational influence on the child from an early age and the wrong measures of parents trying to change the nature of this influence when the child grows up.

The main reason for this error is as follows. There is an objective need for parents to master new technologies and methods of raising a child in modern social conditions (including education). However, mastering these technologies and techniques is difficult due to the lack of time, detailed and complete information on their use, as well as the lack of necessary pedagogical training of parents, which creates a need for the help of specialists. However, it should be noted that such a contradiction has recently revealed a clear and constant trend of improvement.

In addition, the reason for such a mistake in family education is that the field of personal services lags behind industrial development; parents are busy at work, focusing their attention on improving the material and household conditions of life by narrowing cultural and cognitive needs; physical and mental fatigue of parents from work, family problems and adversity of parents and children; drunkenness and quarrels, which arise first of all from the primitive way of family life and the absence of great public interests; lack of new good traditions and customs in the family, etc.

The third common mistake is to consciously (often) give a child complete freedom from an early age, when they are not ready for it and there is not enough guidance for them.

In our opinion, analyzing the above:

First, each error has a complex nature, because it is determined by certain socio-psychological characteristics of the family of the child who grows up in the wrong family.

Second, the aforementioned sets of family characteristics tend to interact. Different combinations of them can cause different types of errors in the same family.

Thirdly, the appearance of the error is possible only due to the interaction of the socio-pedagogical characteristics of the family of the child who grows up in the wrong family. None of these are the direct cause of the error in and of themselves.

Fourthly, one sign can only be decisive or secondary in relation to the circumstances of each individual family.

Fifth, the process of appearance and presence of errors is dynamic. With changes in living conditions and behavior of parents, errors change: one replaces the other or disappears completely.

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